

Cultural Jewellery and Accessories of the Lamkang Tribe

Sungnem Shimla Lamkang and Th. Purnima Devi

Jewellery and accessories constitute an important part of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) that is used to express cultural imagination and experiences. The Lamkang tribe has a unique identification marker of heritage and their culture. The knowledge of weaving, jewellery, and accessories has been passed down from generation to generation and plays a significant role in people's social and cultural lives. This paper uses a survey method study, with interviews as the mode of data collection with community members, artisans, and elders to gather first-hand accounts of the cultural meaning and functions of Jewellery and accessories. Materials are analyzed by collecting through photography and written records. The study found 13 pieces of traditional jewellery and accessories in males and females, nine pieces of jewellery from females, and four from males with photography collected during fieldwork. In the past, each personal adornment had significance and symbolic aspects attached to it. Later on, jewellery was limited to folk dance and festive occasions in the contemporary era. The paper also illustrates the significance of human civilization development in improving accessories created with technology, such as forging and filing techniques; therefore, metal material could be used.

Keywords: Documentation, Traditional Jewellery and Accessories, Lamkang Tribe, Craftmanship, Cultural Heritage

Introduction

Jewellery is one cultural artefact historically linked with the human race. The indigenous craft holds great significance and techniques passed down, especially amongst women. The careful selection of motifs/designs/patterns involves harmonizing various coloured beads, typically procured from nature and nearby markets. As an essential form of art, Jewellery and accessories constitute an important part of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) that reflects living traditions through cultural self-image and aesthetic sensibility. The history of jewellery dates back thousands of years and has multiple uses in different world cultures. The tribes in Manipur are rich in cultural significance and craftsmanship. The traditional ornament design with various materials such as beads,

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feathers, brass, and bronze. The Naga and Kuki people, who are part of various Tibeto-Burman ethnic groups in northeastern India, have a rich tradition of Jewellery and accessories that reflect their unique cultural identity. Manipur has a diverse population, including Meitei, Naga, and Kuki tribes, and traditional tribal outfits with intricate beadwork and accessories. These ornaments symbolize identity and tradition, in this paper, the author will discuss the Jewellery and accessories of the Lamkang tribe in Chandel District of Manipur.

Traditional Jewellery and Accessories

The Cambridge Dictionary defines “Jewellery” as “adornments worn on clothing or the body, usually made from precious materials such as gold and silver, and gemstones” (Edge, 2023). On the other hand, the Oxford English Dictionary’s definition of “Jewellery” emphasizes the materials and their value but does not mention ‘wearability’: “jewels or valuable items typically crafted from gold, silver, or precious stones.” This definition would see Pacific-made or inspired jewellery, which often utilizes local and natural materials such as shells, stones, seeds, feathers, and fibers, as atypical. Jewellery has been designed and worn which is driven by superstition, belief, practices, and emotions (Adnan, 2018; Russell & Russell-Cook, 2018; Mei & Ahmad, 2023). The accessory serves to decorate, hide, and express one’s external feelings in human self-consciousness. Each tribe living in different parts of the world has kept its unique jewellery style intact. The ornament is the art that helps the community to identify and locate their aesthetic art. (Joyce & Kazhgaliuly, 2005; Wadley, 2001; Nikolanko, 2013) mentioned that ethnic ornaments are not just for adornment value but it conveys broader meanings of social, cultural, and identity of ethnic groups and individual wearers in a particular society. Every tribe will have its unique style of jewellery and accessories intact even now, and the Indigenous identity of ornament design has been preserved by ethnic tribes with tremendous responsibility. It is beautiful and communicates messages about the wearer’s status, spiritual beliefs, functional habits, and wealth. It also marks communal celebrations, group associations, and individual means of access (Dwivedi, 2016; Sindhu & Jahan, 2018). The philosophy of preservation is based on the human tendency to preserve cultural values from the past that have significance for future generations. The central government and local government should help the local community with efforts to maintain traditional culture, which helps in preserving their cultural heritage. Jewellery that embodies cultural identity serves as a tangible link to the past. It serves a culture’s stories, values, and aesthetics, making them accessible to future generations. This preservation helps the community in maintaining their cultural diversity with sense of pride and belonging. Jewellery is more than just an accessory; it is often deeply rooted in culture and symbolism. The significance of jewellery can vary significantly across different regions of the world.

Lamkang Tribe

The Lamkang is one amongst 34 tribes of Manipur primarily concentrated in Chandel District of the state. The indigenous knowledge of weaving Jewellery, and accessories has been passed down through generations which plays an important role in people’s

social-cultural lives. Women were skilled in making ornaments by dyeing locally available climber parts, using color extracted from the tree's bark. At the same time, men are skilled in making ornaments using bamboo, tree, cane material, animal parts such as the trunk, horn, tails, and bones, and metal like crude metals, etc. According to the 2011 census there were approximately 9,000 native speakers of the Lamkang dialect, a Tibeto-Burman language. The Lamkang tribe has been recognized as a scheduled tribe by the government of India since 1951. They also communicate with people outside their tribe by speaking languages such as Manipur, Nagamese, English, and Hindi. The Lamkang tribe is easily distinguishable from other tribes in Manipur by their traditional cultural attire (Khular, 2018).

Documentation Perspectives

Documentation is a complex process that includes data acquisition, interpretation, and production stages. It helps in identifying, classifying cultural assets in preventive conservation, monitoring or heritage enforcement in their religious and cultural studies. At the end of the nineteenth century, two pioneers, Paul Otlet and Henri La Fontaine, introduced the term 'documentation' in its technical connotation in library science. The areas of documentation that fall to the library profession's share are documentation work, documentation service, and abstracting work (Neelameghan, 1963). Documentation is one of the central tenets of conservation as a profession and a necessary aspect of the preservation of cultural heritage, which serves to inform the future conservator of the previous work, allowing them to track the efficacy of treatment over time (Beck, 2013). It is impossible unless it is done with the activity of library facets by document selection through acquisition, accessioning, classification, cataloguing, circulation work, and reference service (Putri & Damayanti, 2021; Type, 2024).

What Past Studies Say?

The literature on jewellery and accessories of tribes encompasses a wide range of studies that explore the cultural significance, craftsmanship, and materials used in traditional adornments. Dhaundiyal (2024) studied the van Gujjar women's tradition of bead jewellery, which shows the identity of gender in their community. It focuses on analyzing the beliefs, ideas, and communal perspectives that influence the lives of craftswomen, ultimately providing a nuanced understanding of how gender roles manifest, negotiate, and perpetuate within the unique socio-cultural context of the Van Gujjar community. Kushwaha and Kushwaha's in the same year studied that African Tribal jewellery is made from natural materials such as tiger bone, wood, metal, shells, ivory, bone, stones, and many other natural materials. Each adornment technique carries its narrative. The practices have endured through generations, adapting to shifting contexts while retaining their core significance. The self-adornment techniques of African tribes remind the richness of human diversity and the importance of self-expression within the tapestry of shared global heritage. Bereznitsky (2023) studied the materials used to create the external appearance is based on the energy of ornaments, which helps to create codes of its external, symbolic and worldview content.

The material is associated with the life energy of wild and domestic animals and birds. The peculiarity of the ornamental art of indigenous peoples of the North is the use of fish skin and skins of sea animals.

Chakraborty (2023) in his study, states that the Naga tribe of Nagaland is sought for its aesthetic expressions in the form of different dresses and ornaments. Though the distinct forms of dressing and ornamentations in the sub-tribes of Nagas have cultural and hierarchical significance, the contemporary fashion industry draws inspiration from their primitive art forms and inculcates them in the creative design-making ventures to satisfy the need for unique designs in the fast-growing fashion industry. Ding Liu (2022) examined the feasibility and inventiveness of combining acupoint health-preserving treatment with jewellery design in traditional Chinese medicine from an interdisciplinary perspective. By integrating ergonomics, aesthetics, and TCM acupoints, this thesis creates conceptual jewellery that embodies the three, reflects the harmony of jewellery design, and brings it to life. Belko et al. (2021) provide a detailed analysis of the role of jewellery and accessories in traditional Russian women's costumes from the 16th to 17th centuries, highlighting the intricate designs and materials used in these historical adornments. Additionally, the role of jewellery and accessories in traditional costumes has been examined in the context of Russian culture. The design and production of Jewellery have also been explored, with studies focusing on the 3D CAD (computer-aided design) of jewellery accessories and the use of maritime biota waste as eco-jewellery materials. While there is a wealth of literature on jewellery and accessories from various cultural perspectives, further research is needed to specifically explore the unique traditions and craftsmanship of tribes in India. By delving into the intricate designs and materials used by Indian tribes, a deeper understanding of the cultural significance of jewellery and accessories in India can be gained.

Atamtajani et al. (2021) take a unique approach by discussing the use of maritime biota waste as eco-friendly materials for jewellery design, showcasing the potential for sustainable practices in adornment creation. Arsa & Widiastini (2018) focus on jewellery production in Celuk Village, Bali, Indonesia, a hub for jewellery making and distribution. The study explores the trends, development, and implications of jewellery production in this region, shedding light on the economic and cultural significance of this craft. Kim (2008) explores the vernacular of traditional Korean jewellery, specifically ceramic accessories inspired by the Baek-Jae Muryong Royal Tomb relics, showcasing the fusion of heritage and modern craftsmanship. Young & Kim (2004) focus on predicting online purchase intentions for clothing products, including jewellery and accessories, based on online shopping attributes and demographic variables. This study emphasizes the importance of understanding consumer behavior in the digital age when purchasing adornments.

Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of the study which are as follows:

- To study the significance of different ornaments in identifying the unique culture tribes of the tribe.

- To showcase the traditional skills, artistic creativity, and aesthetics of the tribe.
- To study how tribal accessories incorporate natural elements.
- To identify the different materials used in making the ornaments and their significance.

Research Method, Scope, and Limitations

This paper uses a survey method study, with interviews as the mode of data collection with community members, artisans, and elders to gather first-hand accounts of the cultural meaning and functions of Jewellery and accessories. Materials are analyzed by collecting through photography and written records. Secondary documents such as literature, websites, and other search engines were also analyzed. This methodology provides a holistic approach to understanding the multi-faceted role of Jewellery and accessories in the Lamkang tribe cultures, fostering respect and appreciation for their significance. This paper will focus solely on jewellery and accessories their connection to cultural events. The selected resource persons were elders, artisans, and community members from eight villages, viz. Charang Ching Khunou, Charang Ching Khunkha, Leinganching, Purum Pantha, New Chayang, and Angkhel Chayang, Challong and Diiringkhu, residing in the Chandel District of Manipur, who have indigenous knowledge of jewellery and accessories (This study was carried out from January 2024 to December 2024).

Traditional Jewellery and Accessories of the Lamkang tribe -A Descriptive Analysis

Traditional jewellery techniques often draw their distinctiveness from the specific materials used. The Lamkang males' and females' accessories show the rich traditional attire, which represents their community heritage. Since the dawn of civilization, the tribe used different variety of materials which including metals, gems, ivory, bone, glass, shell, feathers, wood, etc.

Origin of traditional Jewellery and accessories

The historical origins of Lamkang jewellery are not precisely known, like those of other Naga tribes in the northeastern region. The Naga have their own oral stories, through which they pass down accumulated knowledge from one generation to the next. Each natural materials such as bamboo, cane, orchid stems, stone, glass, red-dyed goat's hair, bones, teeth, horns, seashell beads, natural dyes, feathers, and even beetle wings into their ornaments are closely connected to their environment and their nature (Odyuo,2008). The Nagas shares the story of how wearing bead necklaces originated. One day, a young mother, seeking to quiet her restless baby, tied a cotton thread around her neck. The child began playing with the cotton thread, and from then on, the mother faced no issues feeding her baby. Soon, other young mothers began to adopt this method, with some even adding beads, which led to the popularity of the bead necklace, azuki, or 'child holding hands' among all women (Mongro, 1999, p. 85; Odyuo, 2023). Likewise, the Lamkang also have their origins and folktales related to how their traditional dresses and jewellery came to exist. They have used their traditional dresses since the time of civilization. According to Lamkang scholars, the origin and migration of the Lamkang tribe into their present homeland are unknown

but based on oral traditions. After emerging from the cave, they first settled in Khurpii village, from which they further spread to Kokpii, Pheidul, Damdul, and Arhong villages (these places are all abandoned now). Although the exact date and route of the migration could not be ascertained, legends suggest that they migrated from somewhere in the East (Anjana Sankhil, 2012; Sankhil Shelmi, 2010). Another scholar, Avince Anthony (2000), in his thesis, gives the migration of the Lamkang people when they resided in Muru-Sangsang, a location near the sea (near China). From this place, the Lamkang incorporated seashells, ivory, bracelets, and bangles into their cultural dance attire. Lamkang men began wearing garments made from twigs and plant leaves in this settlement. This theory explains how the lamkang used natural resources to make their jewellery and accessories. However, no written records or other forms of evidence support them. Another explanation provided by respondent Db Runghon, age 73, from Challong village, is that while Lamkang resided in their former settlement, the people unearthed red beads because the plants appeared quite distinct from ordinary ones. This discovery was revealed to a man in a dream by God. Consequently, the people excavated the plant and began crafting beads from it (Db Runghon, personal communication, Challong, November 28, 2024). Moreover, another theory suggests that when staying in Haika (the Lamkang old settlement), an old and fertile village, every resource was readily available. This village was large, with abundant natural resources and flourishing food supplies. It was so big that the Tothlang Kam Festival (feast of merit) was held in three places. One end of the village could not hear what happened in the middle of the village, and the middle could not hear the end of the village (Dilbung, 2017). It is said that the reddish Ardei (red beads), which are shown in plate no.5 (female red beads), were extracted from plants in the mountain spring area, with roots spreading underground like potatoes, resembling vine plants when pulled out. Some elders also recounted that Ardei appeared as snails found deep in the jungle near the spring. The migration of the Lamkang people from various places to their final settlement is due to the ongoing conflict with the Khongsai (present-day Kuki) (Sankhil, 2011).

Although the Lamkang people excel in blacksmithing and Jewellery making, their names are not recognized for these skills. They contribute by preserving these traditional crafts and ensuring their presence in modern life. In an interview with Sn. Thamtit age 65, recounted that Lv Thamthi, from his village, was a talented blacksmith in earlier times. He crafted tools for hunting, fishing, and agriculture using iron and brass, as well as jewellery such as armllets and bracelets made from metal and brass (Sn Thamtit, personal communication, Charang Ching Khunou, December 4, 2024). In an interview, another story was narrated by Jv. Peithot age 76 stated that Lv Renghong from Leinganching was a blacksmith; he used to make Haar (bracelet), as shown in the female plate number 8. He melted metals in the fire and shaped them using hollow bamboo Molds before they cooled (Jv. Peithot, personal communication, Charang ching khunou, November 5, 2024).

In the village of Challong, a blacksmith named Db Thamsui, along with his son Db Kamnum and grandson Db Rengtap, all belonged to the same family lineage and were talented craftsmen. They excelled in creating various metal and iron items, including Haar (bracelet) and Chavei (spiral bracelet). These skills were handed down through

generations. Another blacksmith from Challong, Db Thamnok, was also proficient in working with iron and metals and was adept at crafting Haar and Chavei (Db Runghon, personal communication, Challong, November 28, 2024). This account highlights that the Lamkang have been skilled artisans since the dawn of civilization.

Comprehensive guide to Jewellery and Accessories

It draws the guide to Lamkang jewellery and accessories used for both males and females. The complete guide is shown in the Figure given below:

Figure 5.3: A comprehensive guide to Jewellery and Accessories

Classification of Jewellery and Accessories

The table will show the types, the materials used in their preparation, and when and how they are used. Each accessories have their own and different functionality or uses. The classification of the jewellery and accessories are shown in the table 1 below:

Sl. No.	Types of jewellery and accessories	Materials used	Uses
1	Necklaces	Beads	Adornment and festivals
2	Earing	Beads and jewel beetle wing	Adornment
3	Dao & dao-holder	Metal, textile, animal products and wood	Protective, ceremonial & festivals

4	Headgear	Animal products, textiles, cowrie, jewel beetle wings, Quills, bamboo and wood	Festivals
5	Bangle	Metal	Festivals
6	Belt	Metal and textile	Festivals and daily wear
7	Anklelets	Cowrie & shells	Festivals
8	Armlet	Metal, Animal bone and wood	Festivals and hunting

From the above table, different types of jewellery and accessories of the Lamkang are classified as necklaces, earrings, Dao holder, Headgear, Bangle, belts, and ankles. The materials used to create jewellery and accessories are mostly made from natural elements in many ways which include the use of animal products like trunks, teeth, bones, hair, quills and tails are used in making different types of ornaments, mostly used by men in festivals and during hunting. The insect wings and backbone make accessories for women like earrings, headgear, and necklaces, both used by men and women. The plants of some climbers were used as a decorative part in women's headgear making a unique piece. Bamboo is used as a support or creating different shapes used by both men and women. Wood is used in making the dao holder used by men. Market products like Conch shells and cowrie are traditionally used which are made into belts, straps, bracelets, head ornaments, necklaces, and headgear, both for men and women. Conch shells are crafted by going through many lengthy procedures to achieve an antique finish before being made into wearable art pieces. Different colours, shapes, and sizes are used in making necklaces with beads. Women mostly wore cornelian beads, which are transparent. Bangles and armlets were made using brass. Threads of different types of accessories are made using ankle wear, belt, or scarf wear used by both men and women. Crude metal is used by both men and women in making armlets, bangles, and other accessories.

Jewellery and Accessories for Women

There are 9 (nine) accessories found in female jewellery, in which details descriptions, their local names, materials used, and purposes or uses (their functionality is discussed in Table 2, given below:

Table 2: List of Women's Jewellery and Accessories

SI No	Local Name	Description	Material used	Uses
1	Thlumthler (Plate No.1)	It is made from jewel beetle insects and regarded as the most exquisite because of their shiny, hardened, rainbow-like effect which is iridescent and durable. These embellished insect wings were attached to a small white-bead chain.	Jewel Beetle wings, white beads, and thread	Use as earrings or adorned to headgear.

2	Changbom Lukok (Plate No. 2 & 3)	Changbom lukok is the most essential headgear for the Lamkang people, worn during various fairs and festivals. It is made using bamboo, black threads, porcupine quills, and fibers dyed from one climber plant. To make the headgear, a fine strip of bamboo is meticulously mended at both ends and the free ends are properly tied to create a diameter of around 6 to 7 inches to fit one's head. Two decorative, branching structures resembling plants are attached to the ring, with the upright branching-out structures created by clusters of porcupine quills. The lower end of each quill is tied to the ring, and spindle-shaped clusters of dyed fiber are attached to each end of the quills by white paper fold with local adhesive. To add a shining touch, a few long and white cock feathers are also attached between the quills.	Bamboo, thread, porcupine quills, dried fibre, cowrie, cock feather	The headgear of a woman is worn during festivals and fairs.
3	Saishang (Plate No. 4)	It is a cluster of threads knitted in a flat manner used to encircle their calf at the time of dancing. The threads are arranged closely and fastened at regular intervals with the help of another thread. It measures around 10 cm in length. The free ends have tufts of fine colourful woollen fibres. A small glass red glass bead is added at the end of the tip.	A braid tassel threads yellow, black, and red	Used during festivals at the time of dancing
4	Ardei (Plate No.5)	It is a red ivory transparent beads which is commonly worn by women in their day-to-day lives and in the festive season.	Red glass Beads	Worn in daily life & festivals
5	Arlo (Plate No.6)	A long, tube-shaped ivory bead necklace which is typically worn by women.	Ivory beads	Worn during dance
6	Worjari & kep (Plate No. 7)	This set comprises a few items, including a belt decorated with two rows of cowrie shells (wory) & a half conch shell attached at the bottom of the belt with red glass beads. The conch shells contains a strand of thread with red glass beads inside.	Cowrie, red glass beads and belt	Hung at the back during dance in festival
7	Haar (Plate No.8)	Armlet made of crude metal in circular shape. Typical location for wearing these items is on the upper arm of a woman. A white cock feather is adorns on top of the metal to enhance its appearance.	Crude metal	Worn during festivals.
8	Chavei (PI No. 9)	Aspiral golden brass bangles worn by women during festivals and dance.	Zinc & copper	Worn during festivals & dance
9	Shuwlpar (Plate No.10)	The belt comprises seven to eight waxed cotton threads that are beaded together to form a waist tie, allowing the two ends to pin each other. It also features a small spiral golden brass bangle that is inserted and attached in the middle.		During dance and festivals

From the above table, the Women's Jewellery and Accessories it was found that there are nine items listed with their local names, descriptions, material used, and the purposes or the uses of the items. The first local name is 'Thlumthler' which is used as an earring or adornment piece to ear made from a unique jewel beetle insect regarded as the most exquisite of their shiny green hardened rainbow-like effect which is iridescent and durable. It is used in cultural dance during festivals. These jewel beetle insects are found very often nowadays due to environmental factors as they cannot survive in hot and humid areas.

The second item is the Headgear, an object that humans use to cover their heads. It usually has a distinctive crown and brim with different uses, symbolizing identity. The local name is 'Changbom lukok' the most essential headgear for the Lamkang people, worn during various fairs and festivals. It requires a lot of craftsmanship techniques like 'kelki' a kind of climber flower is harvested before it fully blooms and the flower which is like a cotton fiber is dyed to get the pink color as shown in fig 2. Two decorative, branching structures resembling plants are attached to the ring, with the upright branching-out structures created by clusters of porcupine quills. The lower end of each quill is tied to the ring, and spindle-shaped clusters of dyed fibre are attached to each end of the quill by white paper folded with local adhesive. To add a shining touch, a few long and white cock feathers are also attached between the quills.

The third item is 'Saisang', which is a cluster of threads knitted in a flat manner used to encircle their calf at the time of dancing. The threads are arranged closely and fastened at regular intervals with the help of another thread. It measures around 10 cm in length. The free ends have tufts of fine colourful woollen fibres. A small glass red glass bead is added at the end of the tip.

The fourth item 'Ardei' is a red ivory transparent beads which is commonly worn by women in their day-to-day life and in festive season. In olden days these beads were living creature having coiled shell which were found in deep jungle and moist area. This has been the heirloom of the tribe which has been passed on to generation but nowadays this item was replaced by the market beads.

The fifth item is 'Arlo' a long, tube-shaped ivory bead necklace which is typically worn by women during festivals and occasion like marriages and ceremonies.

The sixth item is 'Worjarri and Kep' comprises a few items, including a belt decorated with two rows of cowrie shells (wory) and a half conch shell attached at the bottom of the belt with red glass beads. The conch shells contain a strand of thread with red glass beads inside. This item is worn while performing cultural dance during festival.

The seventh item is 'Haar' armlet made of crude metal which is in circular shape. The typical location for wearing this item is on the upper arm of a women. A white cock feather adorns on top of the metal to enhance its appearance. This armlet is worn during cultural dance in festivals.

The eighth item is 'Chavei' It is a spiral golden brass bangles worn by women during festivals and dance.

The ninth item is 'Shuwlpar' comprises seven to eight waxed cotton threads that are braided together to form a waist tie, allowing the two ends to pin each other. This

item was made from Shuwlpur don (Tender stem of Shuwlpur plant). The tender plants are plucked and twisted together like plaited hair, which is interlacing three or more strands of the plants. which is used as a belt for women, and it also features a small spiral golden brass bangle that is inserted and attached in the middle. In olden days, these items were used on a daily basis, but nowadays it is worn only during ceremonies and festivals.

Plate 1: Thlumthler

Plate 2: Changbom (Accessories)

Plate 3: lukok (Headgear)

Plate 4: Saisang

Plate 5: Ardei

Plate 6: Arlo

Plate 7: Worjari and Kep

Plate 8: Haar

Plate 9: Chavei Plate

10: Shuwlpur

Source: (Photo taken by the author during fieldwork)

Jewellery and Accessories for Men

There are four accessories found in men’s items, in which the local names, details descriptions, materials used, and purposes or uses are discussed below in Table 3 given below:

Table.3 List of male accessories

SI No	Local Name	Description	Material used	Uses
1	Thlumthler (Plate No.1)	This is a male hat or headgear crafted from wild boar skin, Boonie hat shape, and designed with a bamboo pole attached. The Boonie hat’s shape allows for a comfortable fit in the wearer’s head, and the corner of the hat features two lines of cowrie shells circling it. Additionally, there are four ‘Changbom’ placed and decorated at the four corners of the hat.	Bear skin, wood, thread, Quills, Cowrie and plants	Used in cultural dance during festivals

SI No	Local Name	Description	Material used	Uses
2	Wooseng (Plate No.2)	It is a wooden board that features a dao holder, and two hollowed wooden pipes are attached to the front of the board. The strap used to suspend the wooden frame is made from a belt that is decorated with a row of cowries. The frame is suspended from a belt decorated with four rows of cowries, which helps to hold the dao in place.	Wood, belt, and cowries	Used during cultural dance
3	Kaangkol (Plate No.3)	The lamkang used dao in hunting, clearing forest, construction and woodworking. This dao adorned with animal tails which are attached by an animal horn in a conical shape, thlumthler, and white cock feathers is added to make it more attractive.	Iron cowrie. animal tails, horn and insect backbone. Cock feather	Used in cultural dance
4	Kchou (Plate No.4 & 5)	There are two types of kchou worn by lamkang males, one is made from animal bones and the other is made from wood. It is an armlet worn by lamkang males to protect during hunting. The shape of the armlet is U-shaped, according to the size of the man, to fit his arm.	Wood and animal bones	Hunting and during the festive season

From the above table the male jewellery and accessories found were few compared to women, Tomlubuh which is the headgear of the men is specially made from wild bear skin which is found only one headgear in one of the villages due to lack of resources. on top of this the craftsmanship of this headgear requires a lot of attention and details as it could not made from any other animal skin. The Lamkang were a great hunter, they used dao and dao holders not only in hunting but also during construction, clearing of forest and woodworking. They decorated the dao and dao holder by cowrie,

Plate 1: Tomlubuh

Plate 2: Wooseng/worri

horse tails, and cock feathers and the men wear 'kchou' made of wood and animal bones to protect themselves while hunting. In the olden days, all these items were used as cultural significance but nowadays it is used in cultural dance during festivals and ceremonies only.

Plate 3: Kaangkol (Dao)

Plate 4: Kchou (made from wood)

Plate 5: Kchou (made from Animal bones)

Source: (Photo taken by the author during fieldwork)

The significances and values of the motif/design/pattern associated with cultural practices

The motifs, patterns, designs, and materials used by the lamkang tribe in the jewellery and accessories reflect the deep meaning that gives them identity and social structure. The Lamkang motif or design is inspired by the python snake, with its origins rooted in folktales from a time when animals and humans coexisted harmoniously. This story unfolds during one of the grand festivals of the Lamkang. Amidst the traditional celebrations, a snake appeared at a gathering and performed an extraordinary dance. The finest wine was served. Grasping a musical instrument, the snake sang a beautiful war victory song called 'Rel Roo La' in Lamkang, and also recited it as a captivating ballad. The snake's attire was dazzling and eye-catching. The people were amazed by

the splendid ornaments that complemented the dance and the melodious song. The young men, filled with envy, played drums made from pine wood, which the snake feared. Instantly, the snake vanished. It was the envy of the young men that caused them to miss learning the snake's rhythmic dance and the significance of its ornaments. Thus, the motif of male dresses is derived from this tale (Dilbung, 2000). Another story narrated by a respondent, Db Topem, age 72 years (female) and Kh. Beshot age 78 years (male):

Once, a man named Rapa went fishing with his friends in a river. After fishing, they decided to rest under a tree swing. They constructed a ladder to climb the tree and relax. Meanwhile, his friends devised a plan to leave him stranded by removing the ladder. Consequently, Rapa was left alone in the forest. Unable to descend, he waited for someone to pass by. At that moment, a bird called 'Tringrang,' with black and white stripes, appeared carrying a 'worri' (Dao holder) and a 'Kangkol' (Dao). Seeing Rapa sitting on pretending to sit in one of the finest swings and singing "Sildede," the Tringrang asked if it could sit for a while. Rapa agreed and instructed the bird to place the ladder. Once Rapa reached the ground, he hung the dao and its holder, asking the Tringrang, "Do I look good carrying this dao and holder?" The bird replied that it was a sign of great wealth, and there was no reason not to look good. Angered by this, Rapa, being ignorant he threw the ladder away from the tree and took the Tringrang's belongings home, singing "Lamlon Laa." The villagers recognized his arrival upon hearing this. Thus, this dao and the dao holder are said to have been brought from the Tringrang possession by Rapa, and male traditional dress was created from this story. (Db Topem, personal communication, Leiganching, November 29, 2024; Kh Beshot, personal communication, Purum Pantha, October 29, 2024).

Another story of Ratepu based on an interview with Tholung K, age 72 years (how the black and white motif of male dao and dao holder accessories originated)

One day, Tatepu was going for a hunt in the forest. He saw Tringrang (a small bird) in a trap. The bird said to him, please help me release me from this trap? Said Tringrang. what will you give me in return asked the Ratepu. the bird replied that he would give his motif. so, the men dao and dao holder are made from this motif of black and white (Tholung K, personal communication, Leiganching, November 28, 2024).

Ornaments for Hunting

Men accessories are derived from raw materials of animals as they stand a symbol of man's hunting skill and courage. Most of their accessories are used for their purpose, eg, during hunting, hunters wear armlets made from animals to protect themselves. This is because when they shoot their arrows, the string can snap back and cause pain to their bodies.

Ceremonies and Funerary Ornament

The Lamkang used jewellery and accessories in times of marriage and burial rites. In the lamkang culture, it was a custom of bride price in ancient times. Yamlung(gong), Sumpi (flat gong), and other jewellery and accessories like brass armlet and spiral bracelet are given if the family can afford it. They can wear during their cultural festivals and feasts. Some women prefer to wear in their day-to-day life. One of the cultural practices of earlier times, when a person passed away in a village, her family, friends, and relatives would offer her jewellery and accessories. If she already possessed these items, they would be placed in her coffin with the belief that she could use them in the afterlife. This tradition of providing accessories as a final farewell from her loved ones led to a decrease in the availability and originality of locally sourced jewellery and accessories. Some of these original pieces, like accessories and pieces of jewellery, like Har, Chavei, and Arloo, are considered family heirlooms and are quite rare to find these days.

Tools and techniques used for crafting

The Lamkang men were great skilled in blacksmith by smelting, forging into any form and shape. The blacksmith or artisan used Phuum a special type of machine which used for making Haar and other metal accessories. His hunting tools, fishing tools household tools are all made and used since the time of civilization. While women weave by using plants known as Shuwlpur, which is used to make belts, cotton and other resources for making their accessories and jewellery. She used thread, cotton, needle and other materials for making the jewellery and accessories.

Natural dye used by the tribe

The Lamkang women are skilled in making their attire and accessories in different forms. The cotton and natural products which is used in making are cultivated, and some are found abundantly in their villages. Plucking, yarning, spinning, and weaving were considered hobbies and means of livelihood for the young girls and womenfolk in ancient times. The use of dyeing and the yarn or clothes they used certain kinds of roots and bark of a tree or creepers plants. The Lamkang people are much like their neighbouring Naga tribe, and have a strong connection to their surroundings and natural resources. According to a 65-year-old respondent named Sn. Thamtit, the Lamkang utilize natural materials such as bamboo, cane, beetle wings, quills, stones, naturally dyed products, seashell beads, and horse tail or hair in their ornaments. They are very skilled in utilizing natural dyes derived from locally available resources, such as sumac ash for black colouring (Sn Thamtit, personal communication, Charang Ching Khunou, December 4, 2024). According to an interview with Th Khinok, aged 63, she recounted ancestral tales of Sumnungpu (a name she couldn't recall, Sumnung was his granddaughter's name). One day, Sumnungpu pondered how to turn white cloth black. He burned sumac wood, collected the charcoal, and ground it using a Shum (a pestle and mortar used by the Lamkang for grinding rice). He then soaked his white cloth in the crushed sumac ash powder. Initially, people and villagers laughed at him, but once the cloth dried, it was shiny, and the black cloth he wore in the fields resisted dirt. From then on, others began to follow his method. The Lamkang people

are also skilled in using natural products for dyeing their jewellery and accessories. Each motif and style are inspired by the natural products that are available to them (Th Khinok, personal communication, Charang Ching Khunou, December 5, 2024).

For red dye, the Lamkang used the bark of the Pardung tree (known as Sahi in Manipuri), which must be fully mature. The bark is removed and boiled for about an hour, after which the liquid is extracted, leaving only the red-colored liquid. Cloth or thread is then dipped into this liquid to achieve the red color. This liquid also serves as a natural preservative, protecting materials from rot and decay. This tree bark is also used as a preservative method when making other material culture.

For the pink colour, the plant known as “Sonrei,” a type of creeper, is used by extracting its roots and boiling them in a clean pot for thirty minutes, during which they turn a pinkish hue. This plant has extremely coarse leaves that can cause blisters upon skin contact. The resulting pink dye is utilized for colouring the accessories of headgear and other garments worn by women.

Discussion

The descriptive analysis of the study shows the importance of intangible cultural heritage such as the safeguarding of traditional craftsmanship of the Lamkang tribe is in need for of an hour which is in danger of disappearing the resources and skills due to the decline in the members of practitioners, growing disinterest of young people, and lack of funds. The bearer of the heritage should continue to develop their knowledge and skills to transmit to younger generations. The different types of handicraft products are entirely oriented to locally available raw materials. Women play an important role in preserving local culture, namely as bearers of traditional values and in maintaining cultural heritage. The artisans are the ‘living human treasures,’ which UNESCO identifies as ‘knowledge bearers’ or knowledge banks for the tribe elders, should be introduced in the state or district. This will aim at ensuring the viability of the intangible cultural heritage and the skills of craftsmanship, including identification, documentation, research, preservation, protection, promotion, and enhancement for the future. While cultural heritage holds great importance, most preservation efforts have concentrated on digitizing and recording tangible aspects, such as culturally significant objects and locations. However, traditional crafts encompass more than physical artifacts, materials, and tools; they also include craftsmanship as an intangible cultural heritage. This intangible dimension comprises skills like dexterity, expertise, proficient tool usage, and the traditions and identity of the communities where these crafts are or were practiced.

Changing role of Jewellery and accessories in the present scenario

Modernization and socio-economic changes have transformed how Lamkang jewellery and accessories are produced and used. While many natural resources once utilized for crafting ornaments remain available, others have become difficult to access due to environmental changes or a decline in the transfer of traditional knowledge.

Most traditional items are now recreated using market-based materials such as brass, crude metals, or synthetic threads, often for sale or display during cultural events. Despite this, many elders and skilled artisans continue to preserve traditional

techniques. The once-skilled artisans no longer exist, as there are no skills passed on to their younger generation. Natural dyes derived from materials such as sumac ash (for black), Pardung tree bark (for red), and Sonrei creeper roots (for pink) are no longer used; instead, color dye from the market is used for quick and easy results.

The beads that are found in nature are extinct and have been replaced by plastic beads bought from the market. The abundantly available elephant trunks are now replaced by plastic products. Women still play a significant role in preserving the craft of weaving and ornamentation, though such skills are no longer seen as a primary livelihood but rather as cultural heritage practices.

The function of jewellery in cultural rituals has also shifted. While once used regularly in rituals such as bride price negotiations or funerary rites, these practices are now selectively maintained or symbolically performed during festivals and cultural programs.

Nevertheless, the motifs, especially those drawn from folktales, continue to offer a strong sense of identity and pride. The preservation of these stories and designs ensures their continuity in the face of rapid cultural transformation.

Conclusion

Although the heritage of weaving, jewellery, and accessory-making from the Lamkang tribe has been passed down through generations and plays a significant role in the socio-cultural lives of the people, only a few community bearers continue to develop their knowledge and skills to pass on to younger generations. Jewellery is an essential accessory in both men's and women's attire, representing the rich heritage of the community. There is no denying that understanding handicrafts requires grasping the cultural, social, and economic evolution that has profoundly impacted the lives of the people. All the items found are culturally symbolic and are exclusively worn during festivals and special occasions. Most have been passed down through generations and are used by the community. Future generations can be encouraged to appreciate the historical items of the Lamkang tribe instead of valuing foreign ones. Additionally, the community can raise funds internally since most of these items are made from locally sourced materials that are easily accessible and cost-effective.

List of resource persons (10 female & 16 male):

Db Koting (age 61), male elder from Angkhel Chayang. Interviewed on December 9, 2024.

Db Thampor (age 62), male elder from Leinganching. Interviewed on November 20, 2024.

Db. Topem (age 72), female cultivator from Leinganching village. Interviewed on November 20, 2024.

Db Shetit (age 68), male assistant pastor from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on December 4, 2024.

Dilbung Thamdok (age 55), male former lamkang president from Angkhel Chayang. Interviewed on August 9, 2024.

Dilbung Thamnok (age 54), male cultivator from Leinganching. Interviewed on November 20, 2024.

Jv. Mary (age 61), female artisan from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on December 4, 2024.

Jv. Peithot (age 76), female elder from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on December 4, 2024.

Jv. Shumwar (age 65), female artisan from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on December 4, 2024.

Kh Beshot (age 79), male writer, folk singer, and artisan from Purum Pantha. Interviewed on December 10, 2024.

Khular Renghong (age 81), male retired executive secretary, L.NBA from P/Ralringkhu village. Interviewed on July 2 2024.

Leivon Rolly (age 48), male teacher from Challong village. Interviewed on October 29, 2024

Lv. Rengtoi (age 72), male ex-pastor from Charang Ching Khunkha village. Interviewed on November 2, 2024.

Loveson Silshi (age 48), male social worker from Diiringkhu (lamkang Colony). Interviewed on October 29, 2024.

Runghon Db (age 73), male elder from Challong village, Interviewed on 28 November 2024.

Sk Bungtap (age 80) Male elder from New Chayang. Interviewed on December 6, 2024.

Sn Monok (age 78), male elder from Charang Ching khunou. Interviewed on November 10, 2024.

Sn. Shangtin (age 70), female cultivator from Leinganching. Interviewed on December 20, 2024.

Sn. Shongkarnol (age 67), male elder from Angkhel Chayang. Interviewed on November 9, 2024.

Sn. Teshot, (age 67), female cultivator from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on December 8, 2024.

Sn. Thamtin (age 62), female cultivator from Leinganching. Interviewed on November 20, 2024.

Sn. Thamtit (age 65), male elder from the Charang Ching. interviewed on December 4, 2024.

Sn. Tobinsing (age 66), female artisan from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on November 5, 2024.

Th Khungtin (age 79), female artisan from Charang Ching Khunkha. Interviewed on August 7, 2024.

Th Khinok (age 63), female artisan from Charang Ching Khunou. Interviewed on December 5, 2024

Tholung K (age 72), male Lamkang tribe Art and cultural secretary from Leinganching. Interviewed on December 4, 2024.

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